

TRANSNATURE

Policy Recommendations: Julian Alps

Governance

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Introduction

Transboundary cooperation in the field of biodiversity protection is a relatively understudied governance mechanism in Europe. The project “[TRANSNATURE](#) – TRANSboundary governance models of biodiversity protection: case studies for an enhanced protection of NATURAL resources in Europe” filled this gap by focusing on four case studies, including the Julian Alps at the border between Italy and Slovenia. The precise area of cooperation studied in the project, to which these recommendations apply, is that including the territories of the Julian Prealps Natural Park (PNPG), Italy, and the Triglav National Park (TNP), as well as the enlarged area of cooperation included in the UNESCO MAB Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve (JATBR), recognized in July 2024.

Map of the JATBR (gray area) and of the national parks (green areas)¹

After intensive fieldwork carried out between April and December 2024 (21 interviews and 1 focus groups), policy recommendations (PRs) have been formulated to suggest avenues to improve the current mechanisms of cross-border cooperation in the Julian Alps, and ultimately to strengthen biodiversity conservation and sustainable development in the study area. Recommendations focus on the following aspects: finding a balance between biodiversity

¹ Credits: Triglav National Park. This map has been downloaded from this website: <https://biosferaalpigiulie.it/en/biosfera-transfrontaliera/>, and is extrapolated from the Visitor Guide of the Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve, available at: https://www.tnp.si/media/5822/jatbr_visitor_guide_2024.pdf.

protection and local development, improving public participation and local ownership, the importance of data for decision making, the improvement of horizontal and vertical coordination mechanisms, and capacity building needs of both the institutions and the local population.

Recommendations draw extensively from the inputs on challenges and visions collected during the fieldwork. The main categories of stakeholders involved in interviews and the focus group were park authorities, national authorities, national specialized agencies, subnational authorities, local authorities, farmers, hunters, youth representatives, tourism organizations, environmental organizations, local biodiversity experts, regional organizations, and international experts on biodiversity cooperation.

The first draft of the recommendations was prepared in September 2025. This draft was presented and discussed online and with simultaneous interpretation (Italian-Slovenian) with local stakeholders on October 1, 2025. The categories of stakeholders present at the meeting were Italian and Slovenian park authorities, Italian municipalities, Slovenian NGOs, researchers, Italian and Slovenian farmers, youth representatives, and the Italian subnational authority (Friuli Venezia Giulia Autonomous Region). Additional NGOs, as well as Italian and Slovenian national authorities that were invited to the meeting but could not attend, were consulted bilaterally and via email at different stages until December 2025. These exchanges have confirmed the relevance of the proposed actions for the Julian Alps.

Based on the comments received, including regarding the prioritization and feasibility of proposed actions, recommendations were amended to reflect more the needs and sensitivities of concerned stakeholders and authorities than the initial draft. First, in response to the comments received, an effort has been made to frame the recommendations within the existing legal and policy framework (e.g., EU Nature Directives and related national and subnational implementing legislation, as well as biodiversity strategies at all levels). References, where needed, are indicated in footnote. However, to foster a fully-fledged transboundary governance, actions that go beyond the current policy framework are in our view necessary and indicated in some recommended actions. Suggested actions are intended also to contribute to the implementation by decision-makers and local stakeholders of the new obligations of the EU Nature Restoration Law, which is part of the current legal and policy framework applicable to the Julian Alps in need of implementation.²

Second, to reflect the priorities indicated by local stakeholders, recommendations were reorganized by ranking them from the ones that represent the highest priority for the territory to the ones identified as less pressing. This ranking does not necessarily reflect the perceived feasibility of the proposed recommendations: for instance, PR 1 about the balance between biodiversity protection and other societal needs was largely indicated as the most difficult to achieve. As authors of the recommendations we decided, however, to prioritize the most urgent recommendations because, although being the most difficult to realize, they represent in our view essential steps for effective transboundary biodiversity protection in the study area. Proposed recommendations are interrelated to one another, and these links are indicated and briefly discussed within each recommendation (see Connection with other PRs).

² F. Cittadino, E. Mitrotta, H. Schoukens, and N. van der Burgt, TRANSNATURE Policy brief. Transboundary Biodiversity Protection under International and EU Law: Avenues for Reform towards Ecological Unity, January 2026, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.18324680](https://zenodo.org/records/18324680), available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/18324680>.

Third, again in response to the feedback gathered, recommendations are structured as follows:

- each recommendation is numbered to reflect local priorities, where No 1 has the highest priority and No 5 the lowest;
- a clear title summarizing the main action recommended is indicated;
- title is followed by a brief description of the main problem that the recommendation wishes to address;
- a short description of the recommendation is included;
- each recommendation is fully articulated in a table indicating concrete actions where responsible authorities and groups are clearly indicated as addressees, implementation steps, an indicative time frame, and indicators to monitor the achievement of suggested actions;
- connections with other recommendations are indicated;
- the added value of the suggested course of action is clearly spelled out.

Regarding addressees, we identified those that, to our knowledge, are the best suited to promoting some actions. This does not exclude that some of the actions proposed might be promoted also by subjects that are not explicitly listed in the tables. If not otherwise specified, general categories (e.g., local authorities) are referred to both Italian and Slovenian representatives. In some cases, actions recommended to one set of addresses are closely connected to actions targeted at other stakeholders (e.g., see actions of PR 3). Our purpose was to show both that some actions may require the collaboration of more actors and to specify which actions are recommended per stakeholder group. Adaptation of the table to local realities, political opportunities, political will, culture of collaboration, and political sensitivities is highly encouraged.

Concerning the time frame of implementation steps, short-term refers to a period of approximately 1 year, medium-term to 2-5 years, and long-term to 5-10 years. Timeframes, however, are only suggestions that need to be discussed internally to check for local feasibility and adaptation to existing policy processes.

Indicators are included for facilitating the monitoring of proposed actions and implementation steps over time. These have been partially derived from the codebook on how to evaluate effectiveness of transboundary biodiversity protection as part of a TRANSNATURE academic paper currently under publication.

Finally, we acknowledge that all the suggested actions necessitate a permanent flow of public and private funds. While the present PRs focus on governance aspects, another set of recommendations has been developed to cover financial issues. In particular, given the persistent budgetary limitations in the field of biodiversity protection, financial recommendations deal with either optimizing existing financial instruments or exploring

untested mechanisms. These are available online³ and can offer inputs on gathering additional resources useful to implement some of the more pressing solutions identified below. Adequate funding is essential to implement those measures and is premised on political will and prioritization of biodiversity protection.⁴

³ L. Cetara, TRANSNATURE Policy Recommendations: Julian Alps. Funding Opportunities, September 2025, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.20660586](https://zenodo.org/records/20660586), available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/20660586>.

⁴ For instance, available Italian funds useful to implement the proposed actions are those related to the Italian Strategy for Internal areas (<https://politichecoesione.governo.it/it/politica-di-coesione/strategie-tematiche-e-territoriali/strategie-territoriali/strategia-nazionale-aree-interne-snai/>) and to the 2030 Italian Biodiversity Strategy (https://www.mase.gov.it/portale/documents/d/guest/finbz10_pda_snb2030_approvato-csr_26-02-26-pdf).

List of abbreviations

CLLD	Community-Led Local Development
CSOs	Civil society organizations
ECST	European Charter for Sustainable Tourism
EGTC	European Grouping of Territorial Cooperation
EU	European Union
EUSALP	European Strategy for the Alpine Region
FVG	Friuli Venezia Giulia
ISPRA	National Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (Italy)
IT	Italian or Italy
JATBR	Julian Alps UNESCO MAB Transboundary Biosphere Reserve
MAB	Man and Biosphere
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
PNPG	Julian Prealps Natural Park
PR(s)	Policy Recommendation(s)
SI	Slovenian or Slovenia
TNP	Triglav National Park
TRANSNATURE	TRANSboundary governance models of biodiversity protection: case studies for an enhanced protection of NATURAL resources in Europe
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WISO	Large Carnivores, Wild Ungulates and Society Working Group of the Alpine Convention

Policy Recommendation 1

Balancing biodiversity conservation with local development and resource use

Main problem:

Biodiversity conservation in the Julian Alps is often perceived as a constraint for the development of economic activities. In the Julian Alps, the limited opportunities of economic development have resulted in depopulation, especially on the Italian side, and shifts from primary activities to tourism, particularly in Slovenia, with a gradual loss of traditional activities and negative impacts on biodiversity as well (e.g., low-quality reforestation, loss of pastures and cultivated areas). Territorial actors are not always aware of the economic benefits deriving from biodiversity conservation, struggle to find responses to their difficulties and concrete concerns (e.g., large carnivores), and are not always equipped to access existing solutions (e.g., incentives and compensation measures). The link between local development and biodiversity protection must therefore be addressed with specific measures to reinforce mutual benefits and tackle biodiversity loss outside protected areas. Supporting sustainable development opportunities would hopefully increase trust among local stakeholders and motivate them to play an active role in biodiversity protection.

Recommendation:

Adopting an ecosystem approach in the Julian Alps to reconcile nature and human needs.⁵ Enhancing long-term presence in the area by giving people concrete opportunities to stay in the Julian Alps and make a living out of sustainable activities that are in line with the preservation of nature. Establishing incentives to provide economic benefits linked to biodiversity conservation. Improving vertical and horizontal coordination to enable the integration of biodiversity concerns into relevant sectoral policies (e.g., agriculture, tourism, spatial planning, transport), including across the border, to reduce unsustainable uses and practices and ecological fragmentation, and foster conservation actions outside protected areas and Natura 2000 sites.

⁵ The ecosystem approach entails the integrated management of land, water and living resources, and recognizes human contribution to many ecosystems. Ecosystem approach, UNEP/CBD/COP/5/23, Decision V/6, 15-26 May 2000, <https://www.cbd.int/decision/cop/default.shtml?id=7148>.

Addresses	Action(s)	Implementation steps	Time horizon	Indicators
IT/SI Ministries or other competent national authorities	1.1 Prioritizing transboundary ecological corridors	1.1.1 Amending national strategies to include ecological corridors at all levels (national, regional, cross-border) ⁶	Medium-term	1.1.1.a Number of coordination tables with subnational authorities/ competent bodies, including across border, to implement 1.1.1 1.1.1.b Number of ecological corridors established at each level
		1.1.2 Pursuing connectivity beyond protected areas ⁷	Medium-to long-term	1.1.2.a Number of corridors established that extend beyond protected areas and Natura 2000 sites
	1.2 Supporting transboundary biodiversity protection to be articulated at lower governance levels	1.2.1 Signing agreements or MoUs on specific issues to facilitate cross-border economic and research activities or delegating powers to lower governance levels to this end (e.g., on data sharing as in 3.1.4, on the mutual recognition of permits for local farmers markets, for the creation of a	Medium-term	1.2.1.a Agreements/MoUs signed on specific issues

⁶ For instance, the 2030 Italian Biodiversity Strategy (action A.3 at p. 26) foresees national corridors only – between and within Italian regions – but this action should rather have a comprehensive character and go beyond national borders.

⁷ In line with the obligations foreseen in the Nature Restoration Law and the preservation of EU-relevant species and habitats, see TRANSNATURE policy brief (footnote 2).

		JATBR territorial brand (1.19.3) and cross-border value chains, for other economic, agriculture and commercial issues)		
	1.3 Aligning sectoral national policies (e.g., agriculture) with EU Biodiversity Strategy targets (PR 4)	1.3.1 Providing a national framework to integrate 10% of agricultural areas with high-diversity landscape features ⁸ (such as buffer zones, hedges, and non-productive trees)	Short-term	1.3.1.a % of agricultural land integrated with high-diversity landscape features
		1.3.2 Providing a national framework that requires the allocation of at least 25% of agricultural land to organic farming to reduce synthetic chemical use and promote agroecological practices ⁹	Short-term	1.3.2.a % of agricultural land allocated to organic farming 1.3.2.b % of reduction of synthetic chemicals 1.3.2.c List of agroecological practices adopted
	1.4 Allocating funds to economic activities compatible with/promoting biodiversity conservation	1.4.1 Extending Environmental Economic Zones ¹⁰ (<i>Zone economiche ambientali</i>) to regional parks and natural reserves in Italy,	Short-to medium-term	1.4.1.a Law amended in Italy 1.4.1.b Legislation adopted in Slovenia

⁸ As requested by the EU Biodiversity Strategy, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52020DC0380>. See also the Italian Biodiversity Strategy, action B.6 at pp. 41-42.

⁹ As requested by the EU Biodiversity Strategy, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52020DC0380>. See also the Italian Biodiversity Strategy, actions B.7 and B.8 at pp. 41-43.

¹⁰ These zones were established by the so-called Climate Decree-Law n. 111 of 14 October 2019 – amended and converted into Law No. 141 of 12 December 2019 – to support environmentally friendly economic activities within protected national areas, by offering tax incentives and benefits to local authorities and businesses operating there. In the 2030 Italian Biodiversity Strategy these zones are mentioned in sub-action A5.1.d.

		and establish an equivalent in Slovenia		
		1.4.2 Publishing calls for Environmental Economic Zones to fund eco-friendly activities (e.g., ecological farming and sustainable tourism) for micro and small enterprises	Medium-term	1.4.2.a Number of eco-friendly activities funded in both countries 1.4.2.b Number of micro and small enterprises involved in both countries
	1.5 Supporting legislative reforms to include environmental and nature protection tools in relevant sectors	1.5.1 Capitalizing on existing studies and projects dealing with biodiversity integration in relevant sectors ¹¹	Short-term	1.5.1.a List of relevant studies and project identified
		1.5.2 Allocating budget for additional studies/expert support to assess legislative reforms needed and identify specific nature protection tools for relevant sectors	Short-term	1.5.1.a Budget allocated to studies/expert support
		1.5.3 Initiating/mandating studies on the assessment of sectoral legislative reforms needed and the identification of specific nature protection tools for relevant sectors ¹²	Medium-term	1.5.3.a Assessment studies developed

¹¹ As indicated in the TRANSNATURE Policy Brief (footnote 2), this action should be also undertaken at EU level.

¹² For instance, from the interviews emerged that in Slovenia greater integration should be pursued in sectors such as traffic, forestry in state-owned forests, and spatial planning. Regarding traffic, while the Triglav National Park Act (Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 52/10 of 30 June 2010) foresees a traffic regime on a state road for the purpose of nature protection in the park, the Roads Act does not provide for this and is not supplemented with environmental conservation tools. State-owned forests in Slovenia are managed by a company, which aims to maximize profits without considering the public interest in nature protection; therefore, state-owned forests in national parks and Natura 2000 areas are not managed in line with nature protection objectives. This situation could change if management would be devolved to national park managers. As for spatial planning, this is not foreseen at regional level, which could ensure greater connectivity between protected areas and

		1.5.4 Creating “biodiversity contracts” ¹³ similar to river contracts (art. 59 <i>D.lgs.</i> 152/2006 IT) ¹⁴ to be concluded locally between competent planning authorities to help integrate biodiversity protection in local plans and streamline any inconsistencies	Medium-term	1.5.4.a Biodiversity contracts created 1.5.4.b Number of contracts adopted by competent planning authorities within 5 years
	1.6 Liasing with Austrian authorities for the potential enlargement of the JATBR with the involvement of the parks (TNP, PNGP and Dobratsch Nature Park) ¹⁵	1.6.1 Scheduling meetings to discuss the potential enlargement and steps needed to this end at Ministerial level	Medium-term	1.6.1.a Number of meetings organized
		1.6.2 Ensuring public consultation regarding the JATBR expansion process	Medium-to long-term	1.6.2.a Public consultation process organized in the three countries 1.6.2.b Number of stakeholders involved in the three countries

Natura 2000 areas. The Regions Act in Slovenia is missing for lack of political support. Spatial planning at national level is too general, while it partially operates at local level; therefore, ecological corridors and the mosaic of landscape, which are the carriers of biodiversity outside protected areas, are not properly considered.

¹³ These contracts should define concrete actions on how to integrate biodiversity protection in sectoral policies and plans.

¹⁴ For an overview of what they are, see <https://contrattidifiume.mase.gov.it/cosa-sono> accessed 22 September 2025. For an overview of what they are, see <https://contrattidifiume.mase.gov.it/cosa-sono>. For an English source on a different set of river contracts, see <https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/river-contracts-in-flanders>.

¹⁵ The intention to transform the JATBR into a three-countries Transboundary Biosphere Reserve is mentioned in the ‘Candidature of the Julian Alps Transboundary Biosphere Reserve (Italia-Slovenja) of September 2023’ (2023) 104–105 <http://www.julianalps-mab.eu/JulianAlpsTBR_Nomination_Form.pdf>, p. 31.

		1.6.3 Signing a dedicated agreement among the three competent Ministries in Austria, Italy and Slovenia to formally initiate the process of enlargement ¹⁶	Medium- to long-term	1.6.3.a Agreement signed
Competent authorities at national (including Ministries), regional, and local levels	1.7 Monitoring the impact of economic activities on biodiversity and vice versa (PR 3)	1.7.1 Developing sustainability indicators of economic activities (including impact on micro and mesofauna) ¹⁷	Short-term	1.7.1.a Number of indicators identified
		1.7.2 Identifying an assessment baseline year and carrying out periodic monitoring	Short-term	1.7.2.a Monitoring completed every year
	1.8 Tackling the protection of endangered local species (e.g., native sheep species) attacked by large carnivores, wolves in particular ¹⁸	1.8.1 Setting up appropriate strategies and connected action plans	Short- to medium-term	1.8.1.a Strategies adopted 1.8.1.b Action plans developed 1.8.1.c Periodic assessment of the strategy and potential update
		1.8.2 Creating buffer zones around farms	Short- to medium-term	1.8.2.a Buffer zones created within 5 years

¹⁶ A preventive step would be the creation of a National Julian Alps MAB Reserve by Austria, which is currently missing, to be later adjoined to the existing JATBR.

¹⁷ For Italy, these indicators could be developed on the basis of the 2030 Italian Biodiversity Strategy.

¹⁸ The latest modification of the EU Habitat Directive, in 2025, has changed the protection status of the wolves from “strictly protected” to “protected”.

		1.8.3 Halting excessive reforestation	Medium- to long-term	1.8.3.a New forestry management measures undertaken within 5 and 10 years
		1.8.4 Enlarging pasture areas to increase the number of livestock and of active farmers	Medium- to long-term	1.8.4.a % of pasture areas enlarged within 5 and 10 years
	1.9 Allocating funds to economic activities compatible with/promoting biodiversity conservation in connection with 1.4	1.9.1 Mapping available incentives to identify and eliminate negative ones	Short-term	1.9.1.a Mapping exercise completed 1.9.1.b Number of negative incentives identified and removed
		1.9.2 Improving incentives and restoration measures ¹⁹ for damage by macro-fauna and large carnivores and climate change, including by re-allocating budget deriving from 1.9.1 and paying special attention to small-scale farmers	Short- to medium-term	1.9.2.a Budget allocated (or re-allocated) to incentives and restoration measures 1.9.2.b Number of beneficiaries each year
		1.9.3 Investing financial resources in, among others, technological solutions and digital tools to detect and forecast the presence of	Short- to medium-term	1.9.3.a Budget allocated to prevention measures within 1 year

¹⁹ According to local stakeholders, farmers in particular, compensation should internalize costs of wildlife management (e.g., wolves) and climate change (e.g., droughts or extreme events) and foresee cost recovery for lost and lower production. Despite the legitimacy of this request, EU law does not provide for cost recovery for lost and lower production linked to large carnivores' damage, which hinders improvements in restoration measures at national and subnational levels too.

		wildlife in the proximity of farms		1.9.3.b Solutions implemented within 5 years 1.9.3.c Assessment of solutions adopted after 1 year
		1.9.4 Introducing new incentives for economic operators that contribute to productions (e.g., organic farming and dairy products) and supply chains that value biodiversity protection or have a low to zero impact on biodiversity, facilitating access to funds for small-scale farmers	Short-term	1.9.4.a New incentives foreseen 1.9.4.b Special awarding criteria for small-scale farmers foreseen 1.9.4.c Number of beneficiaries per year 1.9.4.d Number of small-farm beneficiaries per year
		1.9.5 Providing economic incentives for the realization of green infrastructures ²⁰ to improve ecological connectivity	Medium-term	1.9.5.a Budget reserved to green infrastructure incentives each year 1.9.5.b Number of green infrastructures funded within 5 years
		1.9.6 Simplifying administrative procedures to obtain compensation (e.g., for damage from wild animals) or financial	Medium-term	1.9.6.a Administrative procedures simplified 1.9.6.b Service desk set up for economic operators

²⁰ In Italy, this objective is in line with the 2030 Italian Biodiversity Strategy, action A3.2 at p. 26.

		incentives for small-scale properties (e.g., for mowing) and helping economic operators navigate administrative requirements with the support of trained staff (PR 5)		1.9.6.c Number of economic operators assisted each year
	1.10 Adopting sectoral guidelines, first nationally and then cross-border, on how to integrate biodiversity protection in other sectors (e.g., agriculture, forest management, tourism) ²¹	1.10.1 Establishing periodic thematic coordination tables (e.g., on the use of natural resources, sustainable tourism, biodiversity conservation and spatial planning, mountain farming, protection of cultural landscape, monitoring) involving competent bodies from relevant sectors to discuss, develop, and periodically update sectoral guidelines	Short- to medium-term	1.10.1.a Number and sectors of authorities involved 1.10.1.b Number of meetings per year (min. 2) 1.10.1.c Sectoral guidelines adopted
		1.10.2 Discussing sectoral guidelines in JATBR Thematic Tables to adapt them to the Julian Alps transnational contexts, and supporting their adoption through	Medium-term	1.10.2.a Number of stakeholders involved 1.10.2.b Number of meetings organized with JATBR Thematic Tables

²¹ Economic activities need to be conceived in a way that is compatible with biodiversity. Sectoral guidelines should cover, for instance, bio-agricultural practices (mowing, right time for hay cutting, diversification of agricultural crops and trees, etc.); sustainable tourism (development of sustainable tourism infrastructures, use of public transportation, appropriate sewage management, creation of quiet zones, prohibition of some outdoor activities in certain areas, appropriate sewage management, etc.); breeding and management of large mammals and carnivores.

		dedicated capacity building (PR 5)		1.10.2.c Capacity building courses organized (PR 5)
	1.11 Requiring respect for ecological corridors in spatial planning developed at subnational level, including to ensure micro-connectivity for micro- and meso-fauna	1.11.1 Approving legislation at competent level and in relevant sectors that preempt derogations to normative acts establishing ecological corridors ²²	Medium-term	1.11.1.a Legislation adopted 1.11.1.b Monitoring obligations on the respect of ecological corridors in subnational spatial planning
		1.11.2 Enhancing ecological corridors to guarantee good ecological status beyond specific habitats and protect species that are not usually targeted (e.g., amphibians, insects, reptiles, birds) but are suffering decreasing trends	Medium-term	1.11.2.a Micro-connectivity foreseen in adopted plans 1.11.2.b Periodic monitoring to assess the ecological status of habitat and species in the ecological corridors
		1.11.3 Foreseeing emergency measures (e.g., cross-border alert obligations) to halt the diffusion of diseases or harmful/invasive organisms in ecological corridors	Short-term	1.11.3.a Emergency measures foreseen in relevant legislation and planning
	1.12 Adopting conservation actions outside protected areas and Natura 2000 sites to enhance biodiversity (e.g.,	1.12.1 Enlarging buffer zones through additional sustainable economic activities (e.g., sustainable farms and sustainable private forests) funded under 1.4.2	Medium-term	1.12.1.a % of buffer zones increased within 5 years 1.12.1.b Number of funded sustainable economic activities included in buffer zones

²² For instance, the FVG Regional Landscape Plan (*Piano paesaggistico regionale*) makes ecological corridors binding for all municipalities, including those outside regional parks and nature reserves.

	through ecological corridors, 1.1)	1.12.2 Reducing or eliminating old or unused infrastructures (e.g., dams, roads or ski resorts)	Medium-term	1.12.2.a Number of old/unused infrastructures reduced or eliminated within 5 years
		1.12.3 Adopting measures focusing on mountain wetlands (e.g., peat bogs) ²³	Short-term	1.12.3.a Specific measures adopted
1.13 Addressing territorial requests and needs in collaboration with the parks (2.3)		1.13.1 Scheduling periodic meetings with the parks to discuss requests and needs collected at territorial level (for instance, by territorial animators 2.5.5) and potential solutions	Short-term	1.13.1.a Number of meetings organized per year 1.13.1.b Summary of the meeting shared with JATBR stakeholders
		1.13.2 Organizing or mandating the organization of capacity building courses on relevant topics, when needs arise (PR 5)	Medium-term	1.13.2.a Capacity building courses organized (PR 5)
1.14 Supporting cooperation in the Julian Alps		1.14.1 Ensuring sufficient funds to be spent for transboundary objectives/activities, for the sound development of the JATBR (e.g., hiring additional staff, implementing the JATBR action plan and	Medium-term	1.14.1.a Additional funds planned within 5 years

²³ According to some stakeholders, mountain wetlands are currently under-protected in the JATBR.

		additional tasks at cross-border level)		
Local authorities	1.15 Raising funds to invest in biodiversity conservation	1.15.1 Enacting a mandatory overnight eco-tax (€1–€3/night) earmarked for conservation goals ²⁴	Medium-term	1.15.1.a Amount of collected tax each year
Alpine Convention	1.16 Liaising with local stakeholders in the Alpine Arc to promote coexistence between large carnivores and humans	1.16.1 Sharing knowledge (e.g., WISO ²⁵ studies, reports, project outcomes) on human-wildlife interaction	Medium-term	1.16.1.a Dissemination of WISO studies/reports to local stakeholders in the Alps
		1.16.2 Setting up a periodic exchange between the JATBR Thematic Table on Agriculture and Forestry and WISO to help address specific needs on human and wildlife interaction in the Julian Alps	Medium-term	1.16.2.a Number of meetings with JATBR bodies per year
Parks	1.17 Keep guiding transboundary biodiversity conservation in the Julian Alps for their roles in the	1.17.1 Collaborating in the development and periodic update of sectoral guidelines (1.10) through JATBR Thematic Tables	Medium-term	1.17.1.a Number of meetings including this point on the agenda 1.17.1.b Guidelines adopted in relevant sectors

²⁴ In this regard see the PR 4 “Institutionalising a Tourism-Based Conservation Fund (TBCF) via Statutory Eco-Tax” proposed in L. Cetara, TRANSNATURE Policy Recommendations: Julian Alps. Funding Opportunities (footnote 3).

²⁵ The main aim of WISO is to find solutions to manage large carnivores and wild ungulates harmoniously with society. For further information on its mandate see: https://www.alpconv.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Organisation/TWB/WISO/WISO_Mandate_2025-2026.pdf.

	Steering Group and JATBR Permanent Secretariat	1.17.2 Raising awareness of the biodiversity value of the Julian Alps, including through improved communication (PR 2), and cross-border educational programs (e.g., Junior Rangers)	Short-term	1.17.2.a Communication campaigns in EN, IT, SI 1.17.2.b Educational program piloted at cross-borders level 1.17.2.c Number of events promoting biodiversity in the area
		1.17.3 Developing a duality of park services by separating the JATBR tasks from other parks' activities (e.g., through 1.14.1)	Medium- to long-term	1.17.3.a Park services differentiated for JATBR with dedicated staff hired
	1.18 Strengthening climate change adaptation and mitigation in the JATBR area ²⁶ by using cohesion funds for cross-border measures	1.18.1 Pursuing joint adaptive management of species and habitats with the aim of identifying common climate adaptation actions targeted at specific species	Short- to medium term	1.18.1.a Measures for adaptive management set up
		1.18.2 Creating a climate change dedicated JATBR Thematic Table or a recurrent session within the European Charter for Sustainable Tourism (ECST) Annual Forum ²⁷	Medium-term	1.18.2.a Climate change JATBR Thematic Table created or recurrent session foreseen in ECST Annual Forum

²⁶ This action would contribute to achieving EU and international biodiversity targets.

²⁷ Yearly event open to the public that allows for periodic evaluation of short- and medium-term objectives linked to EUROPARC certifications.

	1.19 Collaborating with competent authorities at all levels in pursuing transboundary biodiversity conservation	1.19.1 Contributing to monitoring and assessing the impact of economic activities on biodiversity and vice versa (1.7)	Short- to medium-term	1.19.1.a Sharing data on specific species and habitats collected in the context of EU projects, JATBR and Julian Alps Transboundary Ecoregion action plans
		1.19.2 Contributing to addressing territorial requests and needs by liaising with competent national and regional authorities (1.13 and PR 4 – 4.16)	Short-term	1.19.2.a Periodic meetings/survey to collect territorial requests and needs 1.19.2.b Dedicated agenda point in JATBR Thematic Tables
		1.19.3 Fostering the creation of a territorial brand linked to the JATBR ²⁸ for productions and supply chains that value biodiversity protection or have a low to zero impact on biodiversity	Medium-term	1.19.3.a JATBR territorial brand foreseen in the JATBR action planned 1.19.3.b JATBR territorial brand created
		1.19.4 Awarding a territorial brand linked to the JATBR to broaden the potential number of stakeholders involved in the cooperation process, enable the creation of transnational supply chains, and facilitate collaboration among stakeholders	Medium-term	1.19.4.a Number of economic operators applying for the JATBR territorial brand 1.19.4.b Number of economic operators receiving the JATBR territorial brand each year

²⁸ A dedicated territorial brand linked to the JATBR could be awarded to productions and supply chains that value biodiversity protection or have a low to zero impact on biodiversity, like in the case of the “Quality Brand of the Julian Prealps Nature Park” (see <https://www.parcoprealpigiulie.it/it/principale/il-parco-consiglia>) and 100% Valposchiavo (see <https://regione-bernina.ch/progetti/progetto-100-bio-valposchiavo/> and <https://valposchiavo.ch/it/destinazione/100-valposchiavo>).

Farmers	1.20 Contributing to biodiversity conservation through the adoption of compatible agricultural practices, in line with sectoral guidelines (1.10)	1.20.1 Realizing green infrastructure to improve ecological connectivity benefiting from dedicated incentives (1.9.5)	Medium-term	1.20.1.a Number of farmers realizing green infrastructures
		1.20.2 Developing sustainable agricultural productions to benefit from both CAP incentives (eco-schemes, respect for good agricultural and environmental conditions - GAECs, transition payments) ²⁹ and in line with the Farm to Fork Strategy ³⁰ and national incentives (1.4.2 and 1.9.4)	Medium-term	1.20.2.a Number of farmers benefiting from CAP incentives 1.20.2.b Decreased use of pesticides
		1.20.3 Maintaining rural areas and landscape (1.3.1)	Medium-term	1.20.3 % of increased rural areas and landscape
		1.20.4 Contributing to elaborate local strategies on sustainable agriculture and landscape preservation	Short-term	1.20.4.a Number of proposals presented in dedicated meetings or through the collection of territorial requests/needs
	1.21 Participating in cross-border cooperation activities	1.21.1 Participation in JATBR Thematic Table on Agriculture and Forestry	Short- to medium term	1.21.1.a Number of farmers or farmers' associations representatives participating at each meeting

²⁹ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/sustainability/environmental-sustainability/cap-and-environment_en.

³⁰ This Strategy is central to the European Green Deal and aims to set up a comprehensive sustainable food system that contributes to climate neutrality by tackling the nexus between healthy people, healthy societies and a healthy planet. See <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/from-farm-to-fork/>.

		1.21.2 Proposing initiatives that showcase ecological farming practices to inspire new small farmers to adopt them in the JATBR	Short-term	1.21.2.a Agenda topic proposed for the JATBR Thematic Table on Agriculture and Forestry 1.21.2.b Pilot project set up with the support of the parks or competent authorities if needed
Hunters	1.22 Participating in cross-border cooperation activities (PR 2)	1.22.1 Participation in relevant JATBR Thematic Tables	Short-term	1.22.1.a Participation of hunters' representative ensured in relevant meetings
	1.23 Supporting competent authorities and parks in the sustainable management of species	1.23.1 Sharing available data on species collected throughout the years with competent authorities (PR 3)	Short-term	1.23.1.a Existing database shared
		1.23.2 Collecting data to monitor targeted species across the border by applying a common methodology (3.3.3)	Short-term	1.23.2.a Periodic monitoring carried out and database shared
		1.23.3 Contributing to elaborate local strategies on species conservation and management as well as on human-wildlife interaction (1.8 and 1.16)	Short- to medium-term	1.23.3.a Participation of hunters' representative ensured in relevant meetings

Tourism operators	1.24 Collaborating in the identification, development and adoption of sustainable tourism practices	1.24.1 Applying for incentives foreseen for micro and small enterprises developing eco-friendly activities in Environmental Economic Zones (1.4.2), if established, or other relevant incentives (1.9.4)	Short-term	1.24.1.a Number of tourism operators applying for the incentives 1.24.1.b Number of tourism operators benefiting from the incentives
		1.24.2 Contributing to the development of sectoral guidelines (1.10) and adopting them	Medium-term	1.24.2.a Number of tourism operators actively participating in meetings 1.24.2.b Number of tourism operators following sustainable practices identified in the guidelines
		1.24.3 Contributing to the collection of local requests and needs (1.13)	Short-term	1.24.3.a Number of proposals coming from tourism operators
	1.25 Contributing to the cross-border cooperation process	1.25.1 Participating in relevant JATBR Thematic Tables, if invited, ECST Annual Forum and relevant initiatives foreseen in the JATBR Action plan	Short-term	1.25.1.a Number of tourism operators actively participating in meetings 1.25.1.b Number of tourism operators involved in JATBR activities
		1.25.2 Applying for the JATBR territorial brand, once created (1.19.4)	Medium-term	1.25.2.a Number of tourism operators applying for the JATBR territorial brand within 5 years

				1.25.3.b Number of tourism operators awarded within 5 years
Youth	1.26 Contributing to the cross-border cooperation process	1.26.1 Promoting the benefits of biodiversity conservation among their peers, including at professional level (e.g., farmers, hunters, tourism operators) and across the borders	Short-term	1.26.1.a Number of events/activities/meetings organized at local and cross-border levels by youth
		1.26.2 Participating in the development of sectoral guidelines depending on the professional sectors (1.10.2) and promoting their adoption	Medium-term	1.26.2.a Youth representatives actively participating in dedicated meetings 1.26.2.a Number of youth representatives adopting guidelines developed for their professional sector
		1.26.3 Participating in the JATBR Thematic Table on Young People	Short-term	1.26.3.a Youth representatives actively participating in meetings
Experts (e.g., research centers, environmental associations, Universities)	1.27 Supporting parks, local authorities, and stakeholders located and operating in the Julian Alps in enhancing	1.27.1 Providing expert knowledge by capitalizing on ongoing and concluded projects ³¹	Short-term	1.27.1.a Projects outputs disseminated in the JATBR

³¹ Relevant projects are, for instance, Alpslife on monitoring and managing Alpine biodiversity (<https://www.alpine-space.eu/project/alpslife/>) and Humanita on human-nature interaction and impacts of tourism in protected areas (<https://www.eurac.edu/en/projects/humanita>).

	knowledge on transboundary biodiversity protection	1.27.2 Contributing to the development of sectoral guidelines (1.10.2) by providing expert input	Medium-term	1.27.2.a Number of experts actively involved in relevant meetings
	1.28 Contributing to the cross-border cooperation process	1.28.1 Participating in JATBR Thematic Tables on Universities and Research Groups, and relevant initiatives	Short- to medium-term	1.28.1.a Participation of representative ensured in relevant meetings 1.28.1.b Number of experts involved in cross-border initiatives and actions foreseen in the JATBR Action Plan

Connections with other PRs

Connection with PR 2: providing clear guidance on the conservation-development nexus could enhance participation in the governance of the JATBR and Thematic Tables created therein. Such an exchange would also prompt the opportunity to address long-lasting conflicts among local actors by making their perspectives, difficulties and contributions emerge.

Connection with PR 3: territorial actors that perceive the biodiversity value of the Julian Alps and the benefits of cooperation could be willing to share data collected throughout the years.

Connection with PR 4: Integration of biodiversity objectives in sectoral policies is strongly linked with an enhanced vertical and horizontal collaboration among authorities in the Alps.

Connection with PR 5: the adoption of sectoral guidelines and sustainable practices in economic activities would benefit from targeted capacity building initiatives and the support of trained staff in competent authorities and parks.

Added value: Highlights the biodiversity value of the Julian Alps and the common benefits deriving from it; enhances the integration of environmental objectives into relevant sectoral policies; provides sustainable development opportunities to enhance long-term presence and stewardship of the area.

Policy Recommendation 2

Improving effective public participation of relevant actors in the cooperation process

Main problem:

Cooperation in the Julian Alps has gradually developed under the strong leadership of the parks and has produced positive results for transboundary biodiversity conservation. However, these results are not always fully shared or owned by all relevant actors. Participation remains difficult because the process must involve many stakeholders with different, and sometimes conflicting, interests. Furthermore, cooperation is often perceived more as a burden than as an opportunity. Some key groups, especially farmers and hunters, feel marginalized or choose not to engage because they see few direct benefits or have grown disillusioned. This weak local ownership may undermine the otherwise solid collaboration between the parks. In the long term, it could threaten the sustainability of the cooperation process. Stronger inclusion, awareness, and shared territorial responsibility are therefore essential.

Recommendation:

Reinforcing participation mechanisms, by sustaining public engagement through sufficient information and language facilitation, providing adequate funds and resources, making participation count in decision-making, evidencing benefits and mutual gains, exploring new modalities of participation, involving excluded stakeholders, and expanding participation to civil society at large to reinforce the cooperation process.

Examples of priority actions:

Addresses	Action(s)	Implementation steps	Time horizon	Indicators	
Competent Ministries, Region, and authorities, including cooperation with the parks	IT/SI FVG local in with	2.1 Making public participation count in decision-making	2.1.1 Ensuring early engagement of civil society and all concerned stakeholders	Short-term	2.1.1.a Public meetings before decisions are taken
		2.1.2 Sharing relevant information before decisions are taken through dedicated meetings, explanatory dossiers, impact assessments	Short- to medium-term	2.1.2.a Public meetings before decisions are taken	

				<p>2.1.2.b Published informative dossiers in multiple languages, with simplified, less technical information</p> <p>2.1.2.c Notice of public procedures in local newspaper and social media</p> <p>2.1.2.d Respect for legal requirements on impact assessment procedures</p>
		2.1.3 Engaging more closely with affected groups	Short- to medium-term	<p>2.1.3.a Ad-hoc mapping of relevant stakeholders</p> <p>2.1.3.b Discussion of impacts and expectations in dedicated meetings (2.1.2)</p>
		2.1.4 Clearly acknowledging the results of participatory process in decision-making or justifying the exclusion of these results from final decisions	Short- to medium-term	2.1.4 Clear reference to participatory processes and their results in decisions of public authorities
		2.1.5 Creating a fact-finding commission composed of local	Medium- to long-term	2.1.5.a Fact-finding activities performed

		stakeholders to inform decision-making ³²		within the JATBR governance ³³
		2.1.6 Providing sufficient funds for parks and local authorities to promote local participation	Short- to medium-term	2.1.5.b A functioning fact-finding commission established ³⁴ 2.1.6.a Dedicated budget lines or specific funds to promote local participation
Local authorities	2.2 Publicizing the advantages of transboundary biodiversity protection and cooperation	2.2.1 Planning specific campaigns for different targeted groups, including farmers, hunters, and tourism operators ³⁵	Medium-term	2.2.1.a Number or targeted brochures and press releases 2.2.1.b Number of posts on social media per year 2.2.1.c Number of dedicated meetings per year 2.2.1.d Presence of dedicated webpages on institutional websites

³² Fact-finding commissions allow decision-makers and local stakeholders to agree on baseline conditions, common expectations, meaning of technical terms, analysis of current challenges and possible solutions to prevent conflicts and ensure a better implementation of decisions. A successful example of fact-finding commissions is the one instituted in the context of the Scheldt Commission, established by a bilateral treaty between the Netherlands and Flanders (Belgium) in 2005. For more information on this case, see F. Cittadino and others (2025). Exploring Transboundary Biodiversity Protection in Europe: A Comparative Analysis of Four Cases. Eurac Research. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.57749/pwxi-gh94>.

³³ The regional and national levels are involved in the JATBR governance, in the Coordinating Committee, therefore there could be collaboration.

³⁴ Formal legal means to establish these commissions between the FVG Region and Slovenia might be complex due to the uncertainty surrounding the power of regions to conclude treaties with other states. This might require the previous stipulation of treaties between Italy and Slovenia (1.2.1). However, these commissions might be activated either through informal agreements or in the context of existing cross-border cooperation mechanisms, including the JATBR.

³⁵ This implementation step requires a profound knowledge of local communities' needs and expectations. See Action 2.3 below.

		2.2.2 Organizing local promotional festivals and events ³⁶	Short- to medium-term	2.2.2.a Number of promotional festivals per year
		2.2.3 Investing in informational events for municipal schools	Short- to medium-term	2.2.3.a Number of school events organized per year
		2.2.4 Organizing guided tours of natural sites in collaboration with the parks, especially for kids and economic operators ³⁷	Short- to medium term	2.2.4.a Number of organized tours per year 2.2.4.b Number of participants per tour
	2.3 Collecting local needs and ideas (1.13)	2.3.1 Organizing local surveys to understand local priorities, proposals for cross-border cooperation activities, and perceived satisfaction	Short- to medium-term	2.3.1.a Number of surveys per year 2.3.1.b Results of surveys
		2.3.2 Organizing citizen assemblies, either within one municipality or across a group of Italian or Slovenian municipalities ³⁸	Medium-term	2.3.2.a Clear mandate of the citizen assembly and connection to a specific decision-making process or policy 2.3.2.b Published recommendations

³⁶ This means both continuing existing events in the short-term, such as the International Wild Flower Festival (<https://www.bohinja.si/en/international-wild-flower-festival>), local food festivals, and youth summer camps (e.g., <https://www.parcoprealpigiulie.it/it/principale/il-parco-per-i-giovani/summer-camp> and <https://www.parcoprealpigiulie.it/it/principale/il-parco-per-i-giovani/youth-at-the-top>), and planning new ones, including some that take inspiration from activities carried on one side of the borders but are extended to the entire JATBR territory.

³⁷ These tours should be informative and involve local experts that may convey the multiple values of nature during the visits.

³⁸ Citizen assemblies are deliberative tools where “a diverse group of everyday people selected by democratic lottery” meet “to learn, deliberate”, raise awareness, “and adopt recommendations” on different topics (definition partially quoted from the KNOCA website cited later in brackets). Particularly relevant as an example are climate citizen assemblies (see <https://www.knoca.eu/climate-assemblies>). Citizen assemblies in the Julian Alps could focus on future development scenarios, the concrete integration of development needs and protection plans, the role of the JATBR in the next ten years, and others. Citizen assemblies are usually organized by one municipality adopting a formal decision. It is not excluded however that single municipalities can adopt decisions to coordinate a joint citizen assembly, by apportioning roles and budgets.

	2.4 Rewarding participation	2.4.1 Contributing with economic incentives for local stakeholders to participate in cross-border governance, for instance through travel reimbursements, small tokens, organization of common transportation options for attending transboundary meetings, provision of interpretation services, for instance in the context of JATBR activities	Short- to medium-term	2.4.1 Amount of reimbursements, token paid or public money spent on activities facilitating participation per year
		2.4.2 Organizing capacity building activities based on local needs and priorities (5.3 and 5.3.1) ³⁹	Medium-term	2.4.2.a Number of organized courses 2.4.2.b Number of attendees per course 2.4.2.c Categories of course attendees
		2.4.3 Promoting participatory environmental budgeting, including reserved for youth projects ⁴⁰	Short- to medium-term	2.4.3.a Number of participatory budgeting procedures activated per year
Parks	2.5 Sharing information on the cooperation process and on decisions that affect local communities (state of the art, current	2.5.1 Mapping relevant stakeholders and their needs ⁴¹	Short-term	2.5.1.a Variety and comprehensiveness of targeted categories

³⁹ Collected through Implementation steps 2.3.1 and 2.3.2. This activity is fully developed in PR 5.

⁴⁰ Participatory budgeting is a deliberative tool that aims to involve local population in the decisions concerning the allocation of portions of the municipal budget to specific projects and activities proposed by citizens. In Italy, this procedure is to be activated by the municipal council. See e.g., <https://comune.san-dorligo-della-valle.ts.it/it/amministrazione-trasparente-3527/altri-contenuti-3603/partecipazione-160326/bilancio-partecipativo-160327> and <https://www.regione.toscana.it/documents/10180/23652/Cosa%20e%60%20e%20come%20si%20fa%20un%20Bilancio%20Partecipativo/121dc589-2711-4d7b-a510-e60b4174112a>. In Slovenia, municipal participatory budgeting has been enabled in 2018 by the Local Self-Government Act. See e.g., <https://ideas.repec.org/a/ipf/psejou/v46y2022i4p569-589.html> and <https://fiscaltransparency.net/short-info-about-participatory-budgeting-in-slovenia/>.

⁴¹ This can be based and feed in Action 2.3 above.

	actions and related obligations/responsibilities, potential initiatives, opportunities for funding, advantages of participation, advantages of cross-border cooperation)			2.5.1.b Creation and continuous update of a mailing list to distribute awareness raising materials
		2.5.2 Elaborating (online) multilingual guidelines on participatory processes, including deadlines, modalities of deliberation, effects on decision-making processes, to be elaborated every two years	Short- to medium term	2.5.2.a Guidelines published online 2.5.2.b Communication material (websites, brochures, etc.) in both languages
		2.5.3 Distributing and publicizing the minutes of ECST Annual Forum’s meetings in English, Italian, and Slovenian ⁴²	Short-term	2.5.3.a Creation of a mailing list to distribute minutes 2.5.3.b Minutes translated and distributed
		2.5.4 Ensuring simultaneous interpretation in the ECST Annual Forum and in the JATBR Thematic Tables, including through AI tools ⁴³	Short- to medium-term	2.5.4.a Meetings in original language with simultaneous translation
		2.5.5 Creating park territorial animators to be financed by regional/national funds ⁴⁴	Medium-term	2.5.5.a Long-term integration of territorial

⁴² For instance, in another TRANSNATURE case study, the Baltic to Barents, external communication is supported by multilingual websites, social media, visitor centers, press releases, and events. The Bilateral Finnish-Swedish River Commission conducts its work primarily in Finnish and Swedish, with English used where necessary. Main documents are available also in Northern Sámi, Meänkieli, and English. In the Håldi Transboundary Biodiversity Area, Finnish, Norwegian, Sámi, and English are used, while the Pasvik-Inari Transboundary Biodiversity Area also includes Inari Sámi and Russian.

⁴³ Specific funds from regional and national authorities on a rotating basis are needed for that.

⁴⁴ Territorial animators should be ideally fluent in both Slovenian and Italian, knowledgeable to local realities. Their role would be to think of targeted awareness-raising and dissemination activities. They should rely on parks’ contacts and direct knowledge of local stakeholders. Funds to create these positions, ideally as permanent posts, should be provided by regional and national authorities. See Implementation steps 2.1.6 and 1.14.1.

				animators as personnel of the parks
		2.5.6 Monitoring the cooperation process in the ECST Annual Forum and in the Thematic Tables ⁴⁵	Short- to medium-term	2.5.6.a Periodical reports on monitoring available in multiple languages
		2.5.7 Elaborating different communication strategies depending on categories of stakeholders ⁴⁶	Medium-term	2.5.7.a Presence of different communication strategies per stakeholder group
		2.5.8 Organizing a periodic Transboundary Biodiversity Festival with multiple events targeted at different audiences, in cooperation with local stakeholders including researchers and funded by relevant regional and national authorities ⁴⁷	Medium-term	2.5.8.a Number of festivals organized every 5 years 2.5.8.b Number of participants in the festival 2.5.8.c Presence of a dedicated promotional website
	2.6 Using the JATBR Thematic Tables to evidence benefits, discuss common values, and promote discussions on how to	2.6.1 Organizing asynchronous focus groups to collect inputs (online forums) ⁴⁸	Short to medium-term	2.6.1.a Number of online conversations per year

⁴⁵ Monitoring of ongoing and planned activities is already ongoing in the ECST Annual Forum and could be extended to the JATBR Thematic Tables. Also, feedback on specific activities could be collected in a more systematic way, than simply satisfaction expressed in a spontaneous way during meetings, and with a more extended pool of stakeholders. Not all relevant stakeholder categories are indeed represented in the ECST Annual Forum.

⁴⁶ This could be carried out by territorial animators once instituted.

⁴⁷ Useful examples of biodiversity festivals are: <https://fob.nparks.gov.sg/>; <https://www.festivalbiodiversita.it/>; <https://biodiversityfest.it/>; <https://musei.unipa.it/en/events-and-news/festival-della-biodiversita-biodiversity-festival>; <https://www.nbfc.it/en/news/naturalmente-connessi>; <https://www.lifeamphicon.eu/2026/05/28/on-friday-may-22-the-raznozivo-festival-once-again-brought-together-nature-conservation-organisations-from-across-slovenia/>; <https://life-beaver.eu/en/beaver-presentation-at-the-biodiversity-festival/>; <https://www.mcgill.ca/sustainability/commitments/become-nature-positive-university/biodiversity-festival>; <https://ergroup.mu/sustainability/climate-resilience/festival-du-vivant-reclaiming-biodiversity-through-art-and>; <https://www.donegalculture.ie/en/explore/festivals-programmes/biodiversity-week>.

⁴⁸ Asynchronous focus groups are organized as online group discussions where questions are posed to the group by the organizers and individual participants have a range of time (from a few hours to 4-7 days) to respond, even anonymously to the questions posed. Depending on the online platforms used, participants can not only express their views but also interact from a distance with the views expressed by others. Free platforms to launch online group discussions are for instance google groups, the free version of [Miro](#) boards and [padlet](#) boards. There is also professional software that work with a subscription and might be considered in case the online focus group becomes a recurrent cooperation tool.

	integrate biodiversity protection in other sectors			2.6.1.b Number and categories of participants per conversation
		2.6.2 Organizing a transboundary citizen assembly ⁴⁹	Medium-to long-term	2.6.2.a Clear mandate of the citizen assembly and connection to a specific decision-making process or policy 2.6.2.b Published recommendations
	2.7 Improving the involvement of local stakeholders in externally funded projects, also to promote public-private partnerships	2.7.1 Building upon the mapping done in 2.5.1	Short-term	2.7.1.a Variety and comprehensiveness of targeted categories 2.7.1.b Usually excluded categories specifically targeted
		2.7.2 Partnering more with local environmental civil society organizations (CSOs)	Medium-term	2.7.2.a Number of projects involving environmental CSOs within 5 years
2.7.3 Partnering with farmers, hunters, and tourism operators when opportunities arise, at least as		Medium-term	2.7.3.a Number of projects involving farmers, hunters, and tourism operators within 5 years	

⁴⁹ Examples of transboundary citizen assemblies are those organized in the context of the EGCT Euregio Tyrol-South Tyrol-Trentino (see in Italian <https://www.euoparegion.info/it/euregio/progetti/cooperazione/consiglio-delle-cittadine-e-dei-cittadini-delleuregio/>) and the EGTC Eurodistrict Saar-Moselle (see in German <https://www.saarmoselle.org/de/aktuelles/experimentierphase-des-grenzuberschreitenden-buergerinnen-und-buergerrats--n.html>). These assemblies usually require a formal deliberation to regulate their composition, duration, mandate, and other operational details. See footnote 38 for a definition of citizen assemblies.

		beneficiaries or consulted stakeholders ⁵⁰		
		2.7.4 Mapping existing projects in other areas to develop new project ideas ⁵¹	Short-term	2.7.4.a Excel file of existing relevant projects with highlighted points of interest
		2.7.5 Starting b-solution projects that respond to specific local needs	Short- to medium-term	2.7.5.a Number of b-solution projects started within 5 years
		2.7.6 Developing more small-scale projects, such as Community-Led Local Development (CLLD) projects	Short- to medium-term	2.7.6.a Number of small-scale projects started within 5 years
	2.8 Implementing the JATBR Youth Council	2.8.1 Building on the multiannual experience of the Youth Council of the PNPG and of the Italian Biosphere Reserve ⁵²	Short-term	2.8.1.a Meeting(s) to share best practices
		2.8.2 Elaborating a Youth Strategy for the JATBR in collaboration with local youth representatives to identify challenges, priorities, and concrete actions to improve youth involvement	Medium-term	2.8.2.a Published youth strategy as a living document
		2.8.3 Organizing summer camps and other awareness raising activities in the Slovenian side to reinforce relationships with youth	Short- to medium-term	2.8.3.a Number of summer camps organized within 5 years

⁵⁰ There are several examples of successful Interreg and LIFE projects concerning inter alia sustainable farming, wildlife-human coexistence, partnerships with the hunting sector, and sustainable tourism. Few examples are: [Carbon Farming Med](#) (2024-2026), [OliveOilMedNet](#) (2024-2026), and [BEESPOKE](#) (2019-2023), [#soil4nature](#) (2024-2026), [GYPRG](#) (2023-2026), [LIFE WOLFALPS EU](#) (2019-2024), [LECA](#) (2023-2026), [PARTRIDGE](#) (2016-2023), [TranStat](#) (2022-2025), [AMBRA](#) (2025-2027), and [ENRICH-US](#) (2026-2027).

⁵¹ This can be done for instance through the [keep.eu](#) database.

⁵² See <https://biosferaalpigiulie.it/en/the-young-people-of-the-biosphere-reserve/> and <https://www.parcoprealpigiulie.it/it/principale/il-parco-per-i-giovani/consulta-dei-giovani>.

				2.8.3.b Number of school events organized per year
				2.8.3.c Number of festival and other awareness raising events organized within 5 years
		2.8.4 Creating a mobile Youth Center in the area of the JATBR ⁵³	Medium-term	2.8.4.a Established itinerary of the mobile Youth Center
		2.8.5 Partnering with young farmers, hunters, and tourism operators	Medium-term	2.8.5.a Number of initiatives involving young farmers, hunters, and tourism operators within 5 years
				2.8.4.b Number of young participants in parks' and JATBR events and meetings
	2.9 Activating all Thematic Tables foreseen in the JATBR Candidature ⁵⁴	2.9.1 Building upon the mapping done in 2.5.1	Short-term	2.9.1.a Relevance of targeted categories
		2.9.2 Engaging in specific projects as in 2.7	Medium-term	2.9.2.a Number of projects involving relevant categories within 5 years

⁵³ A successful example of this is represented by the *Jugendmobil* operating in the Graubünden canton in Switzerland. See in German https://jugend.gr/app/uploads/jugendmobil_zusammenfassung-evaluation_kurz.pdf or [GaYa Participation Toolbox](#) (2018). As demonstrated by this experience, the mobile Youth Center might be the first step for raising youth interest and creating active groups of young people. The mobile Youth Center could be financed also on a rotating basis by participatory budgeting projects. See Implementation step 2.4.3 above.

⁵⁴ These are: Agriculture and Forestry, Cultural associations, Young people, School and education, and University and Research.

		2.9.3 Planning a timeline to activate all Thematic tables	Short-term	2.9.3.a Timeline published in the yearly JATBR Action Plan
		2.9.4 Identifying obstacles to the activation of some tables and implementing related solutions	Short- to medium-term	2.9.4.a Exchange meetings on that
		2.9.5 Identifying a core group of participants per Thematic Table and foreseeing a rotation of members	Short- to medium-term	2.9.4.a List of members and substitutes published online and updated biannually
	2.10 Rewarding participation	2.10.1 Contributing with economic incentives for local stakeholders to participate in cross-border governance, for instance through travel reimbursements, small tokens, organization of common transportation options for attending transboundary meetings, provision of interpretation services, official roles in the JATBR governance	Short- to medium-term	2.10.1.a Parks' budget reserved for rewarding activities
Farmers, hunters, tourism operators, environmental organizations, researchers, and youth	2.11 Participating in the JATBR governance	2.11.1 Engaging actively in the Thematic Tables	Medium-term ⁵⁵	2.11.1.a Farmers, hunters, tourism operators, environmental organizations, and youth as members in the relevant Thematic Table ⁵⁶

⁵⁵ Whenever created.

⁵⁶ See footnote 54.

		2.11.2 Autonomously identifying and engaging with counterparts in the bordering country, including for the exchange of best practices and the development of autonomous forms of cross-border cooperation	Short- to medium-term	2.11.2.a Number of existing collaborations
		2.11.3 Participating in capacity building opportunities ⁵⁷	Short- to medium term	2.11.3.a Number of farmers participating in courses
Hunters	2.12 Participating in monitoring exercises ⁵⁸	2.12.1 Communicating data to parks and public authorities	Medium- to long-term	2.12.1.a Data shared once/twice per year
Tourism operators	2.13 Contributing to the elaboration of a JATBR strategy on sustainable tourism	2.13.1 Regularly participating in the ECST Annual Forum (1.25.2)	Short- to medium-term	2.13.1.a Number of tourism operators actively participating in meetings

Connections with other PRs

Connection with PR 1: participation as a condition to implement a management approach that truly balances biodiversity protection with local needs.

Connection with PR 3: participation may be enhanced by inclusive monitoring processes.

Connection with PR 5: premised on capacity building, especially when it comes to the involvement of disadvantaged categories or excluded stakeholders.

Added value: Increases the acceptance, ownership, and implementation of the cooperation process by broadening the pool of people committed to it beyond the parks; increases cooperation stability in the long term regardless of political engagement; helps prevent and address societal conflicts, and develop a shared vision for the future of the area.

⁵⁷ See PR 5.

⁵⁸ See PR 4.

Policy Recommendation 3

Sharing and jointly interpreting data on mountain biodiversity on a permanent and regular basis

Main problem:

Monitoring mountain biodiversity in the Julian Alps is complex due to, among others, lack of systematic and permanent data sharing, different approaches to data collection and interpretation adopted across borders, absence of a long-term vision and financial resources devoted to improve joint monitoring, competition among different research groups, lack of a dedicated bilateral/multilateral agreement, and absence of indicators focused on mountain ecosystems. Ensuring an interoperable and constant flow of data is, however, essential for realizing effective conservation policies.

Recommendation:

Realizing a continuous exchange of data on mountain ecosystems and species, by making this exchange a permanent feature, elaborating common interpretation tools to make data interoperable, ensuring adequate funding and political backing, and concentrating on the specificities of mountain ecosystems.

Examples of priority actions:

Adressees	Action(s)	Implementation steps	Time horizon	Indicators
Competent IT and SI Ministries and specialized agencies, as well as FVG Region	3.1. Ensuring institutional support to cross-border monitoring exercises, as well as adequate economic and human resources	3.1.1 Ensuring parallel long-term funding for monitoring all relevant species, ⁵⁹ including species ⁶⁰ outside protected areas and Natura 2000 sites or not listed as endangered or given priority in the Nature Directives ⁶¹	Medium-term	3.1.1.a Existence of specific national or subnational funds to ensure cross-border cooperation 3.1.1.b Existence of specific funds regarding monitoring of specific species

⁵⁹ e.g., the monitoring of mammals is currently financed only through ad hoc externally funded projects in Slovenia.

⁶⁰ Such as amphibians and reptiles, as highlighted by local stakeholders.

⁶¹ This step is fundamental for implementing all actions of PR 3, especially concerning actions that are carried out by parks and local stakeholders that need stable and reliable financial input.

		3.1.2 Providing funds for hiring specific personnel in charge of data collection and monitoring of different species	Medium-term	3.1.2.a Number of hired staff or permanent staff dedicated to perform monitoring duties
		3.1.3 Authorizing the monitoring of relevant species ⁶²	Short-term	3.1.3.a Adoption of official decisions authorizing monitoring 3.1.3.b Ongoing monitoring of some species 3.1.3.c Number of species monitored
		3.1.4 Authorizing the sharing of data, if needed ⁶³	Short-term	3.1.4.a Adoption of official decisions authorizing data openness and exchange 3.1.4.b Ongoing exchange of data on some species
		3.1.5 Concluding MoUs or framework agreements between Italy and Slovenia to authorize data exchange outside EU-funded projects, if needed (1.2.1)	Short-term	3.1.5.a Ongoing discussions to conclude MoUs or agreements 3.1.5.b Number of concluded MoUs or agreements
FVG Region and competent SI Ministries, in collaboration with environmental	3.2. Creating an inventory of all existing databases across borders	3.2.1 Mapping available databases on the Italian and Slovenian sides, including those curated by environmental associations, hunters, or created through ad hoc projects ⁶⁴	Short-term	3.2.1.a Creation of an online, open access, searchable list of existing monitoring databases in the Julian Alps

⁶² e.g., permits to run the monitoring are released in Slovenia by the *Ministrstvo za kmetijsko, gozdarstvo in prehrano* – Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Food.

⁶³ Especially in relation to Actions 3.5 and 3.6.

⁶⁴ e.g., the FVG Region is currently creating an Observatory on Biodiversity (*Osservatorio per la Biodiversità*), a database building on the data collected in the now outdated BIOSTREAM portal, [a project funded by the Fondazione Dolomiti UNESCO](#). The existing regional database for Natura 2000 sites is available here: <https://habitat.regione.fvg.it/mdc/home>, while instructions on how to navigate it are available at this link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3Qb0Z_eMs48. Birds monitoring is assigned

organizations and hunters		3.2.2 Exchanging lists of databases with cross-border counterparts	Short-term	3.2.2.a Organization of a meeting to discuss existing databases
		3.2.3 Identifying gaps in the monitoring of species, both on each side of the border ⁶⁵ and jointly	Medium-term	3.2.3.a Organization of a meeting to discuss monitoring needs
		3.2.4 Prioritizing species for future monitoring actions	Medium-term	3.2.4.a Number of species newly included in monitoring actions
FVG Region and competent SI Ministries, in collaboration with environmental organizations and hunters	3.3 Building upon existing common databases ⁶⁶	3.3.1 Providing funds to continue collection and ensure continuous update of data in existing databases after projects end	Short-term	3.3.1.a Existence of specific funds to continue selected projects 3.3.1.b Dedicated personnel to update data
		3.3.2 Providing funds to make existing databases fully open access and digitalized	Medium-term	3.3.2.a Existence of specific funds for digitalization
		3.3.3 Building a transboundary database drawing upon data jointly collected by hunters ⁶⁷	Short-term	3.3.3.a Concluded MoU or agreement with hunter associations and hunter families to ensure the update of the existing database 3.3.3.b Digitalization and publication of existing database
Parks	3.4. Contributing to the capitalization of	3.4.1 Making existing datasets collected by parks open access and digitalized	Short-term	3.4.1.a Datasets and/or metadata published on parks' websites

to the Birdlife Slovenia DOPPS group; for mammals, some relevant projects are LIFE WOLFALPS (from 2013 to 2018), the LIFE LYNX (2017-2024), and LIFE DINALP BEAR (2014-2019). Hunters have developed their own databases that must be made open access and interpreted jointly

⁶⁵ e.g., pollinators are not monitored in Slovenia.

⁶⁶ See footnote 64. Other relevant projects are: [AlpsLife](#) (2024-2027), [CLIMAPARKS](#) (2010-2013), [Nat2Care](#) (2017-2020), [TRACERKANIN](#) (2021-2022).

⁶⁷ An existing joint monitoring approach in the game species management sector was elaborated already in 2005, where a common software was created to map animals killed or found dead.

	common/existing databases, if relevant	3.4.2 Constantly updating existing databases curated by parks	Medium-term	3.4.2.a Number of new entries/updates every year
		3.4.3 Exchanging good practices as well as errors and implementing successful solutions developed with past projects that did not have continuity	Short-term	3.4.3.a Topic discussed in the meetings of the Steering Committee 3.4.3.b Updates shared in the ECST Annual Forum (EUROPARC)
		3.4.4 Intensifying collaboration with universities, research centers, and associations	Medium-term	3.4.4.a External researchers involved in the update of parks' databases
Parks with support FVG Region and competent SI Ministries	3.5 Creating shared databases on pilot priority species	3.5.1 Identifying priority species for which to start a pilot ⁶⁸	Short- to medium-term	3.5.1.a Meeting to identify priority species 3.5.1.b Inclusion of this monitoring objective in the 5-year Action Plan of the Julian Alps Transboundary Ecoregion (EUROPARC) and in the yearly Action Plan of the JATBR
		3.5.2 Concentrating on data concerning presence and movement of priority species	Short-term	3.5.2.a Data on presence and movement integrated in the pilot database
		3.5.3 Elaborating joint guidelines specifying common baselines and deadlines for data transmission ⁶⁹	Short- to medium-term	3.5.3.a Published guidelines
		3.5.4 Setting up working groups or fact-finding bilateral commissions to ensure data comparability	Short- to medium-term	3.5.4.a Working groups' minutes

⁶⁸ Priority species might go beyond those included in Natura 2000 reporting obligations.

⁶⁹ This implementation step could be carried out also during the staff exchange periods foreseen in the JATBR Action Plan 2025-2026 (project 22, p. 9). Staff exchange could for instance include exchange of rangers, although this measure would probably necessitate resources to ensure language interpretation or facilitation.

		3.5.5 Collaborating with hunters, farmers, environmental organizations, and researchers to detect presence of species, including of large carnivores	Medium-term	3.5.5.a Presence registered outside protected areas
		3.5.6 Once the pilot is tested, extending joint databases to other species	Medium-to long-term	3.5.6.a Availability of data on multiple species
Competent FVG and SI (enforcement) authorities, in collaboration with hunters	3.6 Exchanging data on wildlife crime events ⁷⁰	3.6.1 Improving collection on wildlife crime nationally ⁷¹	Medium-to long-term	3.6.1.a Published reports on wildlife crime episodes
		3.6.2 Testing a pilot by focusing on illegal killing events	Short-term	3.6.2.a Meeting to agree on the pilot's scope 3.6.1.b Inclusion of this monitoring objective in the 5-year Action Plan of the Julian Alps Transboundary Ecoregion (EUOPARC) and in the yearly Action Plan of the JATBR
		3.6.2 Elaborating joint guidelines specifying deadlines for data transmission and other technical parameters	Short-term	3.6.2.a Published guidelines
		3.6.3 Extending the pilot to other illegal acts	Medium-term	3.6.3.a Inclusion of extended objectives in relevant action plans
		3.6.4 Possibly building a transboundary database	Long-term	3.6.4.a Existence of a common repository

⁷⁰ This action might be realized within the framework of the existing collaboration between the Italian Operational Unit for Environmental Surveillance (*Nucleo Operativo per l'Attività di Vigilanza Ambientale* - NOAVA) of FVG and Slovenian forest and police rangers. See D. J. Montalvan Zambrano (2026). Best practices on prevention and enforcement mechanisms against cross-border pollution and wildlife crime. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18377603>.

⁷¹ This is based on consideration shared by local stakeholders in the interview process.

Alpine Convention working groups and/or IUCN	3.7 Developing specific guidelines for monitoring biodiversity of mountain ecosystems and species ⁷²	3.7.1 Elaborating and promoting a red list of threatened species specific to mountain areas ⁷³	Medium-term	3.7.1.a Public red list with indicators 3.7.1.b Number of dissemination events 3.7.1.c Number of specific capacity building opportunities offered (PR 5)
		3.7.2 Specifying priority species for joint monitoring efforts	Medium-to long-term	3.7.2.a Joint resolution/decision on priority species
		3.7.3 Encouraging harmonization among countries about prioritization of endangered mountain species	Medium-to long-term	3.7.3.a Adopted policy advise about legal and policy harmonization
Alpine Convention, also in collaboration with the parks	3.8 Enhancing regional cooperation on common monitoring parameters and techniques	3.8.1 Specifying guidelines for promoting methodological harmonization ⁷⁴	Medium-to long-term	3.8.1.1 Published guidelines
		3.8.2 Promoting multilateral or bilateral agreement(s) to ensure funding capacity for joint monitoring efforts	Medium-term	3.8.2.a Concluded agreement(s) in the Julian Alps
		3.8.3 Disseminating guidelines and common standards to local actors	Medium-to long-term	3.8.3.a Published guidelines 3.8.3.b Organization of dissemination workshops in the Julian Alps/JATBR

⁷² The Alpine Convention's Alpine Biodiversity Action Plan will ideally provide a dataset of species and habitats relevant for the Alps to the Contracting parties.

⁷³ This list might be based on the existing IUCN Red List of Threatened Species: <https://www.iucnredlist.org/>. This red list might inform the selection of priority species for Action 3.5.1.

⁷⁴ These harmonization efforts are currently occurring within the framework of the Biodiversa+ Work Package 2. Biodiversa+ has produced some guidelines. See <https://www.biodiversa.eu/2023/11/13/guide-on-harmonising-biodiversity-monitoring/>. See also <https://www.eurac.edu/en/institutes-centers/institute-for-alpine-environment/projects/biodiversapilot> and <https://www.biodiversa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/european-biodiversity-partnership.pdf>.

				3.8.3.c Number of meetings ensuring vertical coordination
		3.8.4 Organizing capacity building courses on monitoring methodologies (PR 5)	Medium- to long-term	3.8.4.a Number of courses organized per year 3.8.4.b Number of participants in the courses
Hunters, environmental organizations, researchers	3.9 Collaborating in the collection and exchange of data	3.9.1 Contributing to identifying priority species (3.5)	Short- to medium-term	3.9.1.a Meeting organized by competent authorities
		3.9.2 Sharing the results of previous cross-border collaborations on data with competent authorities	Short-term	3.9.2.a Meeting organized by competent authorities 3.9.2.b Participation of relevant groups to the ECST Annual Forum (EUROPARC) or JATBR Thematic Tables

Connections with other PRs

Connection with PR 1: stronger long-term funding and joint monitoring can support a better balance between biodiversity protection and local livelihoods by improving knowledge of species, habitats, and human pressures, including impacts on farming.

Connection with PR 2: involving hunters, environmental organizations, and researchers in monitoring can strengthen their participation in transboundary governance.

Added value: Increases the reliability of data and thus the motivation in sharing them; capitalizes on existing knowledge and avoids duplication; enhances informed decision-making and reinforces the science-policy nexus; enables the evaluation of transboundary cooperation in terms of species trends; facilitates the involvement of local experts and relevant stakeholders and fosters their effective participation in the cooperation process.

Policy Recommendation 4

Improving multilevel governance in the Julian Alps

Main problem:

A genuine multilevel governance framework for transboundary biodiversity protection in the Julian Alps is still lacking since not all the levels of government holding relevant powers on nature conservation are effectively involved in the cooperation process. This is compounded by the fact that the FVG Region and the Slovenian Ministry of Natural Resources and Spatial Planning cannot formally negotiate directly, despite their central roles in managing the two parks. Biodiversity governance is further complicated by its links with multiple policy areas (e.g., tourism, agriculture, hunting, wildlife crime, transport, energy, and spatial planning) where competences are often shared or divided across levels of government. These institutional and legal asymmetries create legislative and policy mismatches between Italy and Slovenia, prevent the emergence of a genuine transboundary vision, hinder coherent management of shared ecosystems, and weaken both vertical and horizontal coordination. Limited staff and insufficient funding further reduce the capacity to sustain effective coordination over time.

Recommendation:

Reinforcing or establishing vertical and horizontal coordination mechanisms among competent authorities at different levels to promote a truly transboundary vision, address legislative, regulatory, and management misalignments, including by ensuring sufficient human resources and enhancing the role of government authorities and politicians in the transboundary cooperation process.

Examples of priority actions:

Addresses	Action(s)	Implementation steps	Time horizon	Indicators
Competent IT/SI Ministries and FVG Region	4.1 Promoting transboundary vision a	4.1.1 Integrating transboundary logic into funding opportunities	Short- to medium-term	4.1.1.a Number of funded initiatives with a transboundary scope
		4.1.2 Stressing the importance of transboundary biodiversity protection in (updated) strategies on biodiversity	Medium-term	4.1.2.a Explicit reference to transboundary biodiversity protection or cross-border cooperation in the field of

				biodiversity protection in national and regional strategies
		4.1.3 Elaborating coordinated measures to enhance ecological connectivity in the form of joint strategies and dedicated parallel funds (PR 1) ⁷⁵	Medium-term	4.1.3.a Joint strategy between Italy and Slovenia on ecological connectivity establishing priority areas developed 4.1.3.a Dedicated budget lines on ecological connectivity
		4.1.4 Facilitating cooperation on the management of and reporting for Natura 2000 sites	Medium-to long-term	4.1.4.a Policy processes for the submission of adjacent Natura 2000 sites coordinated
		4.1.5 Ensuring active cooperation in the Alpine Biodiversity Board of the Alpine Convention and in Action Group 7 of EUSALP ⁷⁶	Short-term	4.1.5.a Responsible national and regional officers participating in these groups
	4.2 Mapping all legislative and regulatory gaps and misalignment, in cooperation with competent counterparts ⁷⁷	4.2.1 Instructing competent departments within each country to collaborate with experts (4.2.3 below) on the mapping of all relevant legislation and plans, including sectoral plans	Short- to medium-term	4.2.1.a Decision on how to organize mapping 4.2.1.b Mapping completed
		4.2.2 Mandating experts to conduct studies to collect relevant legislation and identify legal gaps ⁷⁸	Short- to medium-term	4.2.2.a Experts appointed with a clear mandate
		4.2.3 Studying gaps in specific sectors through externally funded projects	Medium- to long-term	4.2.3.a Number of awarded projects inter alia studying legal and regulatory gaps

⁷⁵ Also in pursuance of Art. 12 of the Protocol on the Conservation of nature of the Alpine Convention. A relevant publication on ecological connectivity as basis for discussion is P. Laner and others, Alpine planning strategy for ecological connectivity. Harmonized and integrated planning of green and blue infrastructure networks in priority areas (2025), available at https://www.alpine-space.eu/wp-content/uploads/2026/03/O1.1_Alpine-planning-strategy-for-ecological-connectivity.pdf. The Platform “Ecological Network” of the Alpine Convention was active in 2007-2016 and could be revitalized to this end.

⁷⁶ See https://alpine-region.eu/topics-action-groups/detail?tx_eusalp_pi2%5Baction%5D=detail&tx_eusalp_pi2%5BactionGroup%5D=8&tx_eusalp_pi2%5Bcontroller%5D=ActionGroup&cHash=fe96391053f809e413b38d613351e609.

⁷⁷ The legislative fields to be mapped should include legislation and regulations not only concerning the management of relevant species (such as the ibex, the chamois, large carnivores and others) and habitats, but also in the field of agriculture, tourism, hunting, wildlife crime, and possibly energy production, as sectors that may drive biodiversity loss.

⁷⁸ This should be done in consultation with the parks and local stakeholders and requires adequate funding similarly to Implementation step 4.3.7.

		4.2.4 Activating Cross-Border Coordination Points or identifying national existing bodies to act as such in pursuance of the newly adopted BRIDGEforEU regulation to address requests for legislative alignment ⁷⁹	Medium-term	4.2.4.a Established coordination points or authority
Competent IT/SI Ministries, FVG Region, and local authorities	4.3 Pursuing horizontal coordination within each country with sectors impacting biodiversity protection, such as tourism, agriculture, transport, energy, and spatial planning	4.3.1 Promoting regular meetings among relevant ministries and regional and local directions, ⁸⁰ including within the Italian Committee on Natural Capital ⁸¹	Short- to medium-term	4.3.1.a Number of meetings held within 5 years
		4.3.2 Exploiting to the fullest the existing connections within national ministries or regional and local departments ⁸²	Short-term	4.3.2.a Periodic meetings across different departments of the same administrative direction
		4.3.3 Establishing links within ministries and regional and local departments when missing, for instance through either regular coordination meetings or the establishment of a biodiversity coordinator overseeing all activities impacting biodiversity, or a dedicated biodiversity coordination unit responsible for implementing biodiversity strategies and overseeing sectoral integration ⁸³	Medium-term	4.3.3.a Number of coordination meetings organized per year 4.3.3.b Coordinated planning of activities 4.3.3.c Creation of biodiversity coordinators or coordination units

⁷⁹ Art. 4-6 Regulation (EU) 2025/925 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 May 2025 on a Border Regions' instrument for development and growth (BRIDGEforEU), available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2025/925/oj/eng>.

⁸⁰ For instance, between environmental ministries and the Ministry of Economy responsible for tourism or the Ministry of Agriculture.

⁸¹ See Art. 67(1) L 221/2015. According to this provision, the Italian Committee on Natural Capital is chaired by the Minister of the Environment, and is composed by a number of other ministries (economy, labor, transport, agriculture and forest, regional affairs, tourism), representatives of the National Association of Italian Municipalities (*Associazione nazionale dei comuni italiani*), the President of the Bank of Italy, the President of the National Statistics Office (*Istituto nazionale di statistica*), and others, as well as competent experts from universities or public administrations (Art. 67(2)). This Committee is inter alia mandated to assist municipalities with the adoption of the environmental budget (Art. 67(3)).

⁸² For instance, the Biodiversity Service (*servizio biodiversità*) direction of the FVG Region is in the same department including agro-food resources, forest, and fish stocks, which creates administrative connections with policy processes in biodiversity-related fields. A similar situation is that of the Slovenian Ministry for Natural Resources and Spatial Planning. Coordination between different departments should in any case be systematized.

⁸³ The latter two options have for instance been implemented in Land Vorarlberg concerning the integration of climate change in public policies and in the Autonomous Province of Bolzano, where a Special Rapporteur for Sustainability (*Incaricato speciale per la sostenibilità*) has been created both at provincial and municipal levels. On the Austrian example, see F. Cittadino and A. Meier (eds.), *Best Practices: Climate Change Policy Integration at the Subnational Level in Italy and Austria: Examples from the Autonomous Provinces of Trento and Bolzano and Länder Vorarlberg and Tyrol* (Eurac Research 2022), available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/7379919> and F. Cittadino and A. Meier, *Policy Recommendations: Climate Change Policy Integration at the Subnational Level in Italy and Austria. Reflections on the Autonomous Provinces of Trento and Bolzano and Länder Vorarlberg and Tyrol* (Eurac Research 2022), available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/7437316>. On the Special Rapporteur on Sustainability, see <https://home.provincia.bz.it/it/contatti/8796>, <https://sostenibilita.provincia.bz.it/it/la-strategia>, and <https://nachhaltigkeit.provinz.bz.it/it/news/in-ogni-comune-verra-nominato-un-responsabile-della-sostenibilita>.

		4.3.4 Coordinating planning processes by aligning deadlines and including biodiversity experts in sectoral planning ⁸⁴	Short- to medium term	4.3.4.a Synergies in sectoral plans Planning processes and deadlines aligned in different sectors 4.3.4.b Biodiversity experts involved in sectoral planning
		4.3.5 Adopting legislation, if necessary, to make sectoral integration mandatory ⁸⁵	Medium- to long-term	4.3.5.a Adopted legislation
		4.3.6 Performing impact assessment procedures, including the evaluation of transboundary impacts ⁸⁶	Short- to medium-term	4.3.5.a (Transboundary) impacts on biodiversity carefully evaluated in public decision-making
		4.3.7 Ensuring sufficient funding to implement reinforced vertical and horizontal coordination, for instance to allow the participation of specific persons per administration in JATBR Thematic Tables	Short- to medium-term	4.3.7.a Specific funds for ensuring vertical and horizontal coordination 4.3.7.b Administration representatives identified to participate in JATBR Thematic Tables
		4.3.8 Amending relevant sectoral legislation or institutions that do not sufficiently take into account biodiversity protection ⁸⁷ (PR 1)	Medium- to long-term	4.3.8.a Norms/Institutions amended to ensure coherence with nature protection acts

⁸⁴ Including in the field of tourism planning at all levels.

⁸⁵ For instance, in the field of tourism planning, an option would be to foresee an integration obligation in the Slovenian Act on the Promotion of Tourism Development.

⁸⁶ Obligations to assess transboundary impacts derive from the Espoo Convention and from Art. 6(3) of the Habitats Directive. See F. Cittadino and others, TRANSNATURE Policy Brief (2026), available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/18324680> (footnote 2).

⁸⁷ Just to give an example suggested by local stakeholders, the Triglav National Park Act stipulates the establishment of a traffic regime on state roads for the purpose of nature protection in the park, but the Roads Act does not provide for this. The result is that the competent Roads Agency of the Republic of Slovenia (*Direkcija RS za ceste*), which operates on the basis of the Roads Act, does not establish a traffic regime. The Roads Act should be amended to reflect the content of the Triglav National Park Act.

	4.4 Participating in the JATBR Thematic Tables ⁸⁸	4.4.1 Mandating permanent staff to participate on a rotating basis	Short- to medium-term	4.4.1.a Staff with specific mandate identified
		4.4.2 Reserving sufficient personal and financial resources for this task avoiding over-delegation to the parks concerning cooperation in biodiversity conservation	Medium-term	4.4.2.a Increased personal resources charged with cross-border cooperation
IT Ministry of the Environment	4.5 Using existing vertical and horizontal coordination mechanisms and establishing ad hoc ⁸⁹ or permanent new ones, if necessary	4.5.1 Regularly meeting within existing vertical coordination mechanisms, such as the State-Regions Conference, ⁹⁰ the Committee for the implementation of the Italian Strategy on biodiversity, ⁹¹ the Italian Committee on Natural Capital ⁹²	Short- to medium-term	4.5.1.a Number of meetings held within 5 years 4.5.1.b Published minutes of coordination meetings 4.5.1.c Involvement of all relevant authorities depending on discussed issues
		4.5.2 Specifically coordinating on the prevention and enforcement of wildlife crime, either with a new coordination body or in the framework of existing ones	Medium-term	4.5.2.a Regular meetings on wildlife crime
SI Ministry for Natural Resources and	4.6 Reinforcing vertical coordination with the local level	4.6.1 Enacting coordination mechanisms with the local level	Medium-term	4.6.1.a Established coordination mechanisms, even on specific issues
		4.6.2 Empowering municipalities and local communities with more staff, resources, and delegated tasks	Medium- to long-term	4.6.2.a Budget allocated for additional staff and tasks

⁸⁸ Also to contribute to Action 4.1.

⁸⁹ Collaboration agreements between the Italian Ministry for the Environment and Italian Regions to adopt Regional Sustainable Development Strategies. See p. 15 Italian Biodiversity Strategy.

⁹⁰ For instance, the Italian Biodiversity Strategy was elaborated in consultation with Regions within the State-Regions Conference.

⁹¹ Created to implement the Italian Biodiversity Strategy, it is structured as a consultation table between the Ministry of the Environment and the regions. It is also open to other stakeholders. The Committee is mandated to identify for each action of the strategy the timetable, the necessary funding sources, and the subjects responsible for its implementation. See Italian Biodiversity Strategy, p. 19.

⁹² See footnote 81.

Spatial Planning⁹³				4.6.2.b Constitutional reforms adopted for the delegation of powers, if politically possible
IT Ministry of the Environment	4.7 Facilitating direct relations between the FVG Region and the Slovenian counterparts at ministerial level	4.7.1 Organizing regular trilateral meetings with the FVG Region and the Slovenian Ministry for Natural Resources and Spatial Planning to share action points, needs, and coordination priorities vis-à-vis the parks	Short- to medium-term	4.7.1.a Number of trilateral meetings organized within 5 years
		4.7.2 Exploring ways to institutionalize direct links between the FVG Region and the Slovenian counterpart (e.g., through delegation of functions in implementation norms – <i>norme di attuazione</i>) ⁹⁴	Medium- to long-term	4.7.2.a Formalized delegation of functions
FVG Region	4.8 Acting as the connecting link between the parks and the JATBR on the one hand and the Italian Ministry of the Environment on the other	4.8.1 Reporting back to the Italian Ministry local dossiers that must be handled at national level, such as legal harmonization needs, coordination needs with the Slovenian counterpart, etc.	Short- to medium-term	4.8.1.a Regular contacts between the FVG Region and the Ministry
	4.9 Participating in negotiating tables about the implementation of the Nature Restoration Law	4.9.1 Contributing to the National Restoration Plan ⁹⁵	Short-term	4.9.1.a FVG Region actively represented in the elaboration process
	4.10 Participating in the JATBR Thematic Tables and the ECST Annual Forum	4.10.1 Guaranteeing enough personal resources to cover those tasks	Short- to medium-term	4.10.1.a Dedicated staff mandated to participate

⁹³ This recommendation is based on the acknowledgment that Slovenia is a unitary country that lacks the subnational or regional level of government, and where municipalities have limited powers and resources. See e.g., <https://www.sgi-network.org/2024/Slovenia/Coordination>.

⁹⁴ This Implementation step would be in line with how *norme di attuazione* have been used in the Autonomous Region Trentino-Alto Adige. Whether this delegation of functions is politically possible in the FVG Region, this should be verified *in concreto*. A change of practice in how *norme di attuazione* are used in FVG might be needed, which would require strong political will and strong majorities.

⁹⁵ See <https://www.mase.gov.it/portale/il-piano-nazionale-di-ripristino-pnr-dell-italia>.

		4.10.2 Reporting back to the competent regional offices	Short- to medium-term	4.10.1.b Regular written reports and meetings
Local authorities	4.11 Clustering to be represented in vertical coordination meetings	4.11.1 Using existing associations ⁹⁶ to reduce the burden of participation on the local level, especially for small municipalities. Association of municipalities could act as representatives of the municipal level	Short-term	4.11.1.a Participation of associations in vertical coordination meetings 4.11.1.b Regular exchanges foreseen among municipalities before and after vertical meetings 4.11.1.c Reports of vertical meetings shared with all municipalities
		4.12 Participating in JATBR Thematic Tables and in the ECST Annual Forum	Short- to medium-term	4.12.1.a Presence of selected representatives
Politicians at relevant levels	4.13 Promoting transboundary political agendas	4.13.1 Liaising with their counterparts on the other side of the border	Medium-term	4.13.1.a Number of transboundary events promoted by or involving politicians
		4.13.2 Promoting the JATBR in public speeches and press releases	Short- to medium-term	4.13.2.a Number of mentions of the JATBR in speeches and press releases per politician per year
		4.13.3 Making transboundary cooperation salient in politics and elections	Medium-term	4.13.3.a Mentions of the JATBR or transboundary cooperation in electoral campaigns

⁹⁶ These are the National Association of Italian Municipalities in Italy (see footnote 81) and the [Skupnost občin Slovenije](#) (Association of Municipalities and Towns of Slovenia).

		4.13.4 Creating biodiversity coordinators or coordination unities ⁹⁷	Medium-term	4.13.4.a Legislation or decrees adopted
	4.14 Participating in the Thematic Tables and in the ECST Annual Forum	4.14.1 Planning presence in politicians' agendas	Short- to medium-term	4.14.1.a Number of politicians present per meeting
Parks	4.15 Involving authorities and politicians in the JATBR governance, including ISPRA experts depending on dossier	4.15.1 Inviting competent authorities and politicians to the relevant Thematic Tables	Short-term	4.15.1.a Number of invitations sent and follow-up emails
	4.16 Representing local needs with subnational and national competent authorities	4.16.1 Facilitating contacts through the JATBR Secretariat	Short- to medium-term	4.16.1.a JATBR Secretariat promoted as contact point
		4.16.2 Clarifying the institutional roles that the FVG Region and Slovenian Ministry for Natural Resources and Spatial Planning play vis-à-vis concerned stakeholders	Short-term	4.16.2.a Creation of a dedicated webpage specifying all roles
		4.16.3 Acting as liaison partner between local stakeholders and national MAB Committees	Short-term	4.16.3.a Clear communication on this role 4.16.3.b Regular exchange with local stakeholders to collect needs/expectations to bring to the National MAB Committee
4.17 Aligning Natura 2000 plans across border in cooperation with competent regional and national authorities ⁹⁸	4.17.1 Aligning management practices, especially among Natura 2000 sites, MAB reserves, and national parks through pilot projects on specific species, best-practice exchanges, and joint monitoring frameworks	Medium- to long-term	4.17.1.a Number of pilot projects initiated within 5 years	

⁹⁷ See Implementation step 4.3.3.

⁹⁸ Difficulties regarding the harmonization of management practices on some species have been referred by park staff.

		4.17.2 Including this priority in the next JATBR Action Plan	Short-term	4.17.2.a Priority included
		4.17.3 Stipulating MoUs or other types of agreements between the PNPG and the TNP to formalize cooperation	Medium- to long-term	4.17.3.a Existence of agreements
IT and SI MAB Committees	4.18 Ensuring direct contact with parks and local stakeholders	4.18.1 Advertising their roles as contact points with local stakeholders	Short- to medium-term	4.18.1.a Documented interactions with local stakeholders

Connections with other PRs

Connection with PR 1: improving dialogue between competent legislative and regulatory authorities might improve the harmonization necessary to ensure a balance between protection and development needs; it might also raise authorities' awareness about local needs.

Connection with PR 2: being more attached to local needs could make responsible authorities more prone to ensure a satisfactory level of funding to improve public participation in the area.

Added value: Reduces governance fragmentation, ensuring more effective and coordinated biodiversity conservation across shared ecosystems both at vertical level between different levels of government and at horizontal level across sectors; helps to overcome localisms and national interests by enabling common policy instruments and alignment in relevant fields; operationalizes the cooperation going beyond ad hoc projects.

Policy Recommendation 5

Enhancing the operativity of administrative entities and territorial actors through capacity building

Main problem:

The establishment of the JATBR and, more generally, the cooperation process triggers opportunities that are not fully captured, especially at local level, due to capacity constraints, complex processes, and the need for specific knowledge/skills. The Julian Alps territory is scarcely populated, with small municipalities and small-scale economic activities (especially on the Italian side). Municipalities can count on limited staff members, are usually overloaded with administrative tasks, and struggle with taking advantage of opportunities linked to transboundary cooperation. Local stakeholders (farmers, entrepreneurs, tourism operators, youth, etc.), instead, would benefit from some support to navigate the complex bureaucracy linked to the use of biodiversity-dedicated funds and incentives, to participate in the cooperation process and, in the case of youth, become trained future local administrators or entrepreneurs.

Recommendation:

Organizing targeted capacity building courses on relevant topics (e.g., functioning of UNESCO MABs or other biodiversity networks, seizing funding opportunities, accessing incentives and compensation procedures, EU project management, language courses, etc.) to increase the involvement of local public entities and territorial stakeholders – located and operating in the JATBR and its surroundings – in the cooperation process and enhancing their operativity in international contexts.

Examples of priority actions:

Addresses	Action(s)	Implementation steps	Time horizon	Indicators
IT/SI Ministries	5.1 Allocating funds, targeted at parks and public entities, for capacity building courses on	5.1.1 Identifying existing funding that could be spent for this purpose	Short-term	5.1.1.a Budget line dedicated to capacity building
		5.1.2 Launching a call to collect expressions of interest of parks and other relevant (sub)national	Short- to medium-term	5.1.2.a Call published 5.1.2.b Mapping interested entities

	transboundary biodiversity conservation	authorities concerning capacity building needs to support the organization of courses in the JATBR area		5.1.2.c Number of channels used to disseminate the call
		5.1.3 Allocating funding to parks and lower administrative levels, if needed, for the organization of courses	Medium-term	5.1.4.a Number of entities with a specific amount of funds allocated
Competent SI national and IT regional authorities	5.2 Organizing capacity building courses for staff of parks and local authorities located in the JATBR and surrounding areas on relevant topics (e.g., access to funds for municipalities in natural areas; incentives for territorial stakeholders; project management)	5.2.1 Collecting capacity building needs of parks and municipalities in the JATBR and surrounding area (in Italy and Slovenia)	Short- to medium-term	5.2.1.a Survey for the collection of capacity building needs sent within 1 year 5.2.1.b Number of municipalities responding to the survey in both countries 5.2.1.c Number of bilateral exchanges organized with municipalities in both countries to clarify specific needs (thematic and linguistic) within 18-24 months
		5.2.2 Based on 5.2.1, organizing thematic capacity building courses in Italian, Slovenian, and possibly English	Medium-term	5.2.2.a Number of thematic courses scheduled in Italian, Slovenian, and English within 5 years 5.2.2.b Number of course participants
		5.2.3 Based on 5.2.1, organizing language courses for staff involved in cooperative/JATBR activities	Short-term	5.2.3.a Number of participants in language courses
	5.3 Setting up fact-finding commission(s) to improve local knowledge (2.2)	5.3.1 Identifying staff, local stakeholders, and experts to be involved in fact-finding commission(s)	Medium- to long-term	5.3.1.a Fact-finding commission(s) established 5.3.1.b Balanced composition ensured
		5.3.2 Ensuring a low turn-over of fact-finding commission members	Medium- to long-term	5.3.2.a Member mandate of at least 2 years

Competent SI national and IT regional authorities, local authorities, and parks	5.4 Organizing capacity building courses targeted at local stakeholders, with the financial support of competent national and regional authorities (5.1.4) and the involvement of territorial animators (2.5.5)	5.4.1 Mapping local needs and priorities of capacity building for targeted stakeholders (e.g., farmers, hunters, tourism operators, environmental and cultural organizations, youth, researchers) by staff involved in JATBR activities	Medium-term	5.4.1.a Number of meetings with targeted stakeholders
		5.4.2 Based on 5.3.1, planning capacity building courses divided per target group (e.g., on sectoral guidelines PR 1) and languages, and opened to participants in JATBR Thematic Tables	Medium-term	5.4.2.a Call for application open for all courses 5.3.2.b Number of applications collected per course 5.3.2.c Number of participants to each course categorized by stakeholder group and language
Local authorities	5.5 Dedicating staff resources to JATBR/cooperative activities	5.5.1 Planning at least one additional staff with specific technical and language skills ⁹⁹	Medium- to long-term	5.5.1.a Number of municipalities (in both countries) allocating budget for the recruitment of additional staff within 12-18 months
		5.5.2 Recruiting staff on a permanent basis	Medium- to long-term	5.5.2.a Number of recruitment procedures for additional staff in both countries within 2 years 5.5.2.b Number of long-term contracts for staff dealing with JATBR/cooperative activities within 5 years

⁹⁹ This action is in line with the Italian Biodiversity Strategy, sub-action A4.1.m at p. 27.

Parks	5.6 Contributing to capacity building efforts at territorial and transboundary level	5.6.1 Collaborating with competent authorities by providing content and contacts for capacity building courses (5.4)	Short-term	5.6.1.a Number of meetings with competent authorities
		5.6.2 Promoting existing courses offered by national and international organizations and networks (e.g., EUROPARC, UNESCO MAB Programme, IUCN) open to park staff and territorial stakeholders, including by covering course fees	Short-term	5.6.2.a Number of courses identified 5.6.2.b Number of posts/articles published on parks' websites to disseminate available opportunities 5.6.2.c Number of sponsored participants (if needed) 5.6.2.d Number of park staff participating in courses (e.g., territorial animators and those involved in cooperative activities)
	5.7 Exchanging staff to build up competences	5.7.1 Organizing regular staff exchanges	Short- to medium-term	5.7.1.a Number of staff exchanged each year
		5.7.2 Organizing joint capacity building activities for staff involved in JATBR/cooperative activities and territorial animators	Short- to medium-term	5.7.2.1 Number of joint capacity building activities activated each year
International organizations and networks dealing with nature protection (e.g., Alparc,	5.8 Contributing to capacity building on transboundary biodiversity protection at local level, by opening existing courses or organizing dedicated ones	5.8.1 Offering courses for territorial stakeholders	Short- to medium-term	5.8.1.a Number of courses open to territorial stakeholders 5.8.1.b Number of posts/articles to promote available courses on JATBR and parks' websites

EUROPARC, UNESCO MAB Programme, IUCN)				5.8.1.c Number of territorial stakeholders from the JATBR participating
		5.8.2 Providing capacity building support in terms of contents, contacts, and funds	Short- to medium-term	5.8.2.a Number of courses co-organized with parks and local entities in the JATBR area
Stakeholders located or operating in the JATBR and surrounding areas (e.g., farmers, hunters, tourism operators, CSOs, youth, researchers)	5.9 Taking advantages of capacity building on transboundary biodiversity protection	5.9.1 Participating in existing and targeted courses as well as actively proposing course topics	Short- to medium-term	5.9.1.a Number of stakeholders participating in each course, categorized by stakeholder group and language

Connections with other PRs

Connection with PR 1: capacity building efforts would enhance knowledge of transboundary biodiversity protection and the benefits deriving from the cooperation process, which might result in a more effective consideration of biodiversity interests in other sectors and economic activities.

Connection with PR 2: capacity building efforts addressed to local stakeholders could reinforce participation of targeted actors in the cooperation process as well as in the JATBR Thematic Tables.

Connection with PR 4: a trained and competent staff of local authorities/municipalities can meaningfully participate in vertical and horizontal coordination tables.

Added value: Ensures more effective participation in the transboundary process and may in the long run enable cross-border exchanges among local administrations or other corresponding categories of stakeholders.